

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND IONIC CONDUCTION OF STRUCTURAL ELECTROLYTES WITH BICONTINUOUS MORPHOLOGIES

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In memoriam of Dr. Joachim H.G. Steinke

Keywords: *structural electrolyte; multifunctional supercapacitor; bicontinuous morphology; epoxy resin; ionic conductivity; mechanical properties*

1 Introduction

Electrolyte systems that can carry mechanical load while allowing for high levels of ionic conductivity are an important prerequisite for structural power storage devices. Introduction of structural power storage into the variety of consumer products will allow saving in weight and volume. Moreover, using a supercapacitor/battery system in hybrid electric vehicles (HEV), the supercapacitor part will extend the battery lifetime by protecting it from the high peak currents. To successfully produce structural power storage requires the development of multifunctional electrolytes where one has to simultaneously maximize mechanical properties and ionic conductivity.

Despite numerous research efforts in this area the challenge remains as to how to retain desirable mechanical properties while imparting ion conductivity.[1-3] To achieve this desired aim, different approaches were explored including addition of inorganic fillers, such as SiO₂, TiO₂,[4, 5] organic fillers, such as cellulose nanowiskers,[6] blending polymers with different properties, etc. [7].

Based on the data available in the literature one of the most promising approaches to maximize multifunctionality for structural power improvement is to utilize the benefits of a bicontinuous phase structure; one phase providing mechanical strength and a second one ion flux. There are number of publications which support this approach [1, 2, 7, 8] even though different types of polymers have been used.

Starting with a polymer which initially possesses low mechanical properties and ionic conductivity, the authors [7] had significantly improved both parameters through the addition of a block copolymer of polyethylene oxide-polypropylene oxide in the presence of LiClO₄ as the electrolyte salt. The addition of 50 wt% block copolymer of polyethylene oxide-polypropylene oxide caused an increase in ionic conductivity from 2.22·10⁻⁹ S/cm for polyethylene oxide+LiClO₄ to 5.51·10⁻⁸ S/cm for the polymer blend (+ LiClO₄) while the Young's modulus, determined using tensile test, rose from 15 MPa to 114 MPa. However, it should be noted that, despite the significant improvement, the ionic conductivity value was still much too low. A different approach in creating a bicontinuous structure was used by F. Gayet et al [1]. Organosilicate compounds, such

as tetramethylorthosilicate and tetraethoxysilane, were used to form a silica bicontinuous network *via* sol-gel process. A mixture of butylmethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide and tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as a reaction medium for the sol-gel process and a polymer electrolyte based on modified polymethylmetacrylate, containing 5 mol% units bearing pendant hydrolysable silicon groups and tetraethoxysilane was prepared. It was reported that the obtained electrolyte had an ionic conductivity as high as 1.01 mS/cm, but a very low Young's modulus of 0.33 MPa.[1] However, the most promising results are reported for electrolyte obtained by modification of the epoxy/amine systems. [2, 8]

The focus on epoxy/amine systems is not a surprise since cured epoxies have an excellent set of the specific properties and wide range of applications from household items to aerospace. Following are two examples of electrolytes based on polymers with epoxy functional groups. Films were formed of poly(ethylene glycol) bis(3-aminopropyl) crosslinked poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether with lithium 3-glycidyloxypropanesulfonyl-trifluoromethanesulfonylimide as comonomer varying the content of latter. It was found that an increasing concentration of sulfonylimide monomer present in the polymer films, improved ionic conductivity from 0.05 mS/cm to 1.0 mS/cm, though their most promising multifunctional polymer resin had an ionic conductivity of 0.76 mS/cm with a Young's modulus of 0.97 MPa.[8]

Bisphenol A based epoxy have also been investigated copolymerized with tetrafunctional epoxy resins and crosslinked with tetraethylenepentamine in the presence of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (EMIM-TFSI). A decrease in the EMIM-TFSI concentration from 50 wt% to 43 wt% resulted in monolithic samples with a Young's modulus increasing by an order of magnitude from 45 to 480 MPa whilst the corresponding ionic conductivity decreased from 1.2 mS/cm to 0.38 mS/cm respectively.[2] However, it should be

noted that there is very limited information on the microstructure of the formed electrolytes and its effect on their overall performance.

Here we report results on how electrolyte/epoxy resin formulations produce different morphologies as a result of reactive phase separation and how the different morphologies correlate with ionic conductivity and mechanical properties (particularly Young's modulus). Since these structural electrolytes are based on commercially available, high performance epoxy resin formulations, our findings are a further step in the direction of scale-up and commercial use of these attractive multifunctional structural power materials.

2 Results and Discussion

In this study three commercially available high performance epoxy resin/amine formulations, MVR444, VTM266, MTM57, have been used. Standard epoxy/amine compositions were mixed with the EMIM-TFSI ionic liquid doped with a lithium salt (bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonylimide lithium salt, LiTFSI) as the electrolyte (EMIM-TFSI+LiTFSI).

Depending on the resin used, two distinctly different types of the microstructure were formed. A representative example of one of the morphologies is shown in Figure 1 as a result of precipitation polymerization from the solution [9, 10]. Electrolytes with a morphology presented in Figure 1 were synthesized using MVR444 and VTM266 epoxy/amine systems. It is worth noting that the scale at which phase separation took place in the formed structural electrolytes is depending on the epoxy/amine system used. In the case of MVR444, a bicontinuous network with the finer structure and smaller pore sizes was formed as compared to VTM266 when the same composition was used.

Figure 1. Representative SEM image of a simple bicontinuous morphology obtained from precipitation polymerisation of VTM266 in EMIM-TFSI+LiTFSI.

The morphology shown in Figure 2 is reminiscent of spinodal decomposition [11] and is characterized by a resin rich phase (closed pore domains) and an ionic liquid rich phase (connected nodular domains). This type of morphology was obtained using epoxy/amine system MTM57. It can be clearly observed that the microstructure of MTM57 based electrolyte comprises three different morphologies. A continuous epoxy network, the cross-section of which has a sea-island structure, most likely formed by the droplets of an electrolyte (EMIM-TFSI + LiTFSI) dispersed in the epoxy bulk, and surrounded by the spherical non uniform nodules. It has to be noted that the nodules did not possess additional structure and formed of bulk epoxy. A microstructure similar to that presented in Figure 2 was reported in the literature. Highly ordered porous polymers were synthesized *via* living polymerisation of vinyl monomers [12]. However, formation of the porous epoxy monolith with similar microstructure was achieved by spinodal decomposition *via* polymerization induced phase separation of epoxy based systems. [11] Nevertheless, the non-uniformity of the spherical nodules can be considered as an evidence that the formation of the microstructure in the studied systems takes place not only *via* spinodal decomposition but *via* combination of different processes.

Figure 2. Representative SEM image of a bicontinuous phase system with a more complex pore morphology obtained from “(mini)emulsion” polymerization of MTM57 in EMIM-TFSI+LiTFSI.

Generally structural electrolytes with a simple bicontinuous morphology (Figure 1) exhibited better mechanical performance but lower ionic conductivity compared to the more complex phase morphology characterized by the presence of connected nodules (Figure 2).

Figure 3 and 4 shows an effect of the struts and pores size of bicontinuous structure (Figure 1) on ionic conductivity and Young’s modulus of the structural electrolytes. For the studied systems, an increase ionic conductivity coincided with a decrease in the Young’s modulus, well known in the literature [10, 13, 14]. It can be seen that ionic conductivity was affected by the changes in the microstructure dimensions to a greater extent than the Young’s modulus. Threefold increase in the struts size led to a nearly seven fold increase in the ionic conductivity (Figure 3a), but only a 0.6 times decrease in Young’s modulus (Figure 3b).

A similar trend was observed when ionic conductivity and Young’s modulus were plotted *vs* pore size (Figure 4 a,b). The increase in the ionic conductivity was most likely a result of the decrease in the tortuosity of the system with increase in the pore size.[15]

Figure 3. Effect of the dimensions of the bicontinuous microstructure on the ionic conductivity (σ) (a) and Young's modulus (b).

The effect of the microstructured dimensions on ionic conductivity and Young's modulus in the more complex structures (Figure 2) was studied using formulations based on epoxy/amine system MTM57. The ratio between MTM57 and ionic liquid (EMMTFSI) was kept constant at 50:50 wt.%. The microstructured dimensions were varied by changing the lithium salt concentration in the structural electrolyte.

As was mentioned earlier, the microstructure of the MTM57 based structural electrolytes comprises of three different structures. It has to be noted that as continuous epoxy phase becomes

finer the spherical nodules which are surrounding it also come to be smaller and more uniform. However, changes in the size of the spherical nodules are less significant compared to the changes in the size of continuous epoxy phase. That is why here only the effect of the continuous epoxy phase on the ionic conductivity and Young's modulus is presented.

Figure 4. Effect of the dimensions of the bicontinuous microstructure on the ionic conductivity (σ) (a) and Young's modulus (b).

Figure 5a shows a nearly linear increase in the ionic conductivity as the continuous epoxy phase (struts) are become bigger. However, effect of the

continuous epoxy phase (struts) on the Young's modulus is less straightforward (Figure 5b). A decrease in the Young's modulus can be observed when size of the continuous epoxy phase increased from $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ to $37 \mu\text{m}$. However, further increase in the continuous epoxy phase to just above $100 \mu\text{m}$ led to a small rise in Young's modulus. To find a reason for such behavior the porosity of the structural electrolytes was studied.

that porosity has an inverted trend compared to Young's modulus, showing that as continuous epoxy phase/struts are getting finer as porosity of the sample decreased and Young's modulus rose. Increase in the ionic conductivity coincides with the increase in the porosity for the samples with continuous epoxy phase size from $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ to $37 \mu\text{m}$. The following sudden drop in porosity did not lead to the expected reduction of the ionic conductivity.

Figure 5. Effect of the dimensions of the more complex, spinodal decomposition like microstructure on the ionic conductivity (σ) (a) and Young's modulus (b).

The effect of the continuous epoxy phase/struts on the porosity is presented in Figure 6. It can be seen

Figure 6. Effect of the continuous epoxy phase/struts on the porosity of the structural electrolyte. Experiment was performed on samples after electrolyte (EMIM-TFSI+LiTFSI) had been extracted.

In summary, for both morphologies it was found that mechanical properties increased with shorter length scales of characteristic features; size of pores and pore wall thickness in the case of the open porous structures, and size of nodules and thickness of closed pore domains in the case of the more complex morphology (as shown in Figure 2).

3 Experimental Part

3.1 Materials

Three fully formulated commercially available epoxy resins with trademarks MVR444, MTM57 and VTM266 were prepared at Cytec. MVR444 is

an amber colored liquid with viscosity of 14.7 Pa·s; MTM57 and VTM266 are white pastes with viscosities of 4835 Pa·s and 1400 Pa·s respectively. 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethyl sulfonyl)imide (EMIM-TFSI, ≥98% (H-NMR), Aldrich), bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide lithium salt (LiTFSI, puriss., ≥99.0% (¹⁹F-NMR Aldrich) and all other chemicals were used as received.

3.2 Sample preparation

Lithium salt was dissolved in the ionic liquid prior adding solution into the jar with the epoxy/amine system. All components were mixed using a speedmixer until a homogeneous mixture was formed. Samples were cured using the following cure cycles: for MVR444 based formulations it was 18 hours at 100°C, for MTM57 based - 1 hour at 120°C and for VTM266 based - 1 hour at 120°C. Samples were cooled in the oven to 60°C prior to their removal.

Samples were cured in two shapes: monoliths with diameter of 1.2 mm and height of 60 mm and flat plaques with thickness of 2.5-3 mm, to allow them to be tested for ionic conduction and mechanical performance. To make them, the mixture was poured into a mould and cured using a time and temperature profile specific for each resin and mentioned above. In case of the plaques, two glass slides treated with release agent LOCTITE 700-NC Frekote were used as a mould.

3.3 Sample characterization

All samples were dried overnight at 80°C under reduced pressure before testing.

Ionic conductivity was measured by dielectric spectroscopy using a Novocontrol broadband dielectric spectrometer in the frequency range of 10⁻²-10⁷ Hz using stainless steel electrodes. The ionic conductivity (σ) was calculated on the base of sample dimensions and bulk resistance (R_b) values which were determined from the high frequency intercept of the impedance curve with the real axis using equation (1).

$$\sigma = \frac{h}{R_b} \quad (1)$$

The thickness (h) of the thin polymer films was determined using a digital calliper with an accuracy of 0.01 mm.

The *mechanical performance* of the cured formulations was assessed using three point bending tests. Experiments were performed using a Zwick testing frame, a 1kN force transducer and an optical Heidenhain displacement transducer. For small deflections and isotropic materials, the Young's modulus taken from bending tests is close to the value obtained from tensile tests. Since the tested materials exhibited a viscoelastic character, the elongation rate was kept constant ($\dot{\epsilon} = 0.05 \text{ min}^{-1}$) for all tests in order to obtain comparable results. To account for the difference in thicknesses for different batches of the structural electrolytes, the anvil speed v was adjusted to the individual sample thickness in order to achieve the same elongation rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ in the surface of each bending sample.

The anvil speed v was adjusted using following equation:

$$v = \frac{\dot{\epsilon} l^2}{6h} \text{ [mm/min]}, \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ dimensionless, not in % -, span l and height h , mm. Samples dimensions were as following: length: 30-35 mm; width: 4mm; thickness: 2 -3mm.

To study the morphology and porous properties of the formulations, EMIM-TFSI and LiTFSI were extracted from the cure formulations as follows. The sample was cut, placed into the glass vial and submerged in ethanol. To increase the rate of diffusion the solvent (ethanol) was exchanged twice a day for at least one week. After that solvent was decanted and sample was dried in a vacuum oven at 70°C under reduced pressure to constant weight. For all samples studied, at least 97 wt.% of the original EMIMTFSI+LiTFSI loading was successfully removed from the cured polymer network.

SEM images of extracted samples were recorded on a Jeol JSM 5610 LV scanning electron microscope with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. All samples were gold sputter coated for 120 s in

an argon atmosphere (Emitech 550, Emitech Ltd., Ashfort, UK) to ensure sufficient electrical conductivity. The dimensions of the microstructure of the samples were determined using ImageJ software.

The skeletal density of the samples was determined by pycnometry using a Helium Pycnometer (AccuPyc 1330, Micrometrics Ltd, Dunstable, UK). This method detecting the pressure change resulting from displacement of gas by a solid object but does not take into account the pores for the calculation of the sample volume. The calculation of the bulk density is done using following equation:

$$\rho_b = \frac{m_s}{V_c - \frac{V_{exp}}{\left(\frac{p_{1g}}{p_{2g}} - 1\right)}} \text{ [g/cm}^3\text{]}, \quad (3)$$

where m_s is the weight of the sample (g), V_c is the pycnometer volume (cm^3), V_{exp} is the expanded volume (cm^3), p_{1g} is the pycnometer elevated pressure, p_{2g} is the pycnometer intermedia pressure.

The envelope density and porosity of the samples was determined using GeoPyc 1360 analyser (Micrometrics Ltd., Dunstable UK). This technique relies on the displacement of a solid object immersed in a bed of much smaller solid particles and the external (envelope) volume of the sample is determined so that the internal pores are considered to be part of the sample. The envelope density is calculated using following equation:

$$\rho_e = \frac{m_s}{V_e} \text{ [g/cm}^3\text{]}, \quad (4)$$

where m_s weight of the sample, g and V_e is the envelope volume, cm^3 .

Knowing values of envelope (ρ_e) and skeletal (ρ_b) densities the porosity (P) of samples can be calculated using the following equation:

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_e}{\rho_b}\right) \times 100(\%), \quad (5).$$

Acknowledgements

Funding from the EU as part of the FP7 project "Storage" (Grant Agreement No. 234236) is gratefully acknowledged. Authors would like to acknowledge help of Mr. Jon Cole with preparation of the initial samples.

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